

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)

ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

**PEER TUTORING INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY AS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL FOR ENHANCING
SENIOR SECONDARY STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN PHYSICS IN GOMBE
STATE, NIGERIA**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17928339>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effectiveness of the Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy in enhancing senior secondary school students' academic performance in Physics in Gombe State, Nigeria. Persistent low achievement in Physics, as reflected in WAEC reports and state performance records, has been linked to teacher-centred instructional methods and limited student engagement. Employing a quasi-experimental design, the study compared the performance of 204 students assigned to experimental (peer tutoring) and control (conventional teaching) groups. Data were collected using pre-test and post-test Physics achievement measures and analysed using mean scores and ANCOVA. Findings revealed a significant improvement in the academic performance of students taught through peer tutoring compared to those exposed to conventional methods ($F = 83.649$, $p < 0.05$), indicating the superiority of peer-assisted learning in promoting conceptual understanding and achievement. Results also showed no significant difference between the performance of male and female students within the peer tutoring group ($F = 1.874$, $p > 0.05$), suggesting that the strategy benefits both genders equally. Additionally, there was no significant interaction effect between teaching method and gender on academic performance ($F = 1.690$, $p > 0.05$), confirming that the effectiveness of peer tutoring is gender-inclusive. The study concludes that peer tutoring is an effective and equitable instructional strategy for improving Physics achievement among senior secondary school students. It is recommended among others that teachers should adopt and integrate structured peer tutoring strategies into physics instruction to improve students' understanding and overall achievement.

Keywords: Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy, Gender, Academic Performance, Physics

INTRODUCTION

Education remains one of the most powerful instruments for promoting scientific, technological, and socio-economic development. It equips learners with the intellectual tools, values, and skills required to understand and contribute meaningfully to a rapidly advancing world. As Akinyemi and Mustapha (2022) emphasize, education is not limited to transmitting facts but serves as a transformative process that empowers individuals to think critically, solve problems, and adapt to emerging global trends. Through formal, informal, and non-formal learning environments, education fosters the development of scientific reasoning and provides the foundation for informed participation in society.

Within the broader educational landscape, science education holds a central position in promoting technological innovation, scientific literacy, and sustainable development. UNESCO (2023) identifies science education as a key driver of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 4 (quality education) and SDG 9 (industry, innovation, and infrastructure). Science education helps learners develop critical inquiry skills, problem-solving abilities, and an understanding of scientific principles necessary for navigating modern life. The World Bank (2022) similarly argues that countries investing in science and technical education demonstrate stronger economic resilience and competitiveness in today's technology-driven global economy.

Among the science subjects taught at the secondary school level, Physics is widely acknowledged as pivotal to scientific and technological advancement. It provides the conceptual and procedural foundations essential for innovations in engineering, medicine, telecommunications, energy, and environmental science. As noted by Kinyota and Kajungu (2024), Physics equips learners with lifelong scientific skills that support inquiry, critical thinking, and technological competence. Banda and Nzabahimana (2021) further highlight the relevance of Physics in daily life and its role in advancing modern technologies.

Despite its importance, Physics is often perceived by students as abstract, difficult, and less appealing compared to other sciences like Biology and Chemistry. Ding, Jiang, and Gapud (2023) report that students frequently develop negative attitudes toward Physics, which contributes to poor engagement and low achievement. Evidence from WAEC Chief Examiners' Reports (2014–2023) confirms that students' performance in Physics across Nigeria, including Gombe State, has remained consistently unsatisfactory. Appendix A from Gombe State further reveals a decade-long decline in academic performance, suggesting that existing instructional practices have not produced the desired improvement. According to Sarma and Bagiati (2021), poor performance in Physics limits students' access to science and technology-oriented careers, thereby affecting national development goals.

Researchers attribute these persistent challenges to several factors: students' negative perceptions of Physics, inadequate laboratory facilities, shortages of instructional materials, and the continuous reliance on teacher-centered methods (Michael et al., 2021). Craker (2021) notes that many learners consider Physics the most difficult of the science subjects, leading to low interest and poor outcomes. Although numerous teaching strategies—such as cooperative, collaborative, inquiry-based and discovery learning—have been recommended (Bello, 2011), studies show that many Physics teachers continue to rely heavily on the lecture method (John, 2016; Ogundola, 2017; Agu & Samuel, 2018), which limits students' active participation and conceptual understanding.

In response to these challenges, researchers have emphasized the need for student-centered instructional strategies capable of enhancing interest, participation, and academic performance. One such strategy is the Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy, a collaborative learning approach in which high-performing students support their peers in understanding academic content. Sam (2016) describes peer tutoring as a learner-centered pedagogy that enhances comprehension, communication skills, and confidence among both tutors and tutees. Peer tutoring also promotes cooperative learning, allowing students to learn from each other in a supportive and less intimidating environment. Toulia, Strogilos, and Avramidis (2023) assert that such environments enhance engagement and improve academic outcomes.

Research demonstrates that peer tutoring is an effective, affordable, and scalable strategy across various subjects. Sam (2016) found that peer tutoring improved the performance of business mathematics and biology students, while Jibrin, Ibrahim, and Zayum (2016) observed that it strengthens both academic and personal development. Despite this evidence, peer

tutoring is still not commonly used in Nigerian Physics classrooms, especially at the senior secondary level, where students struggle the most.

Gender is another factor frequently discussed in Physics education. While some studies report significant differences in performance between male and female students (Amogne, 2015; Olasehinde & Olatoye, 2018; Owodunni & Ogundola, 2018), others indicate no significant difference (Hashim et al., 2015; Lin, 2015). Voyer and Voyer (2014) even report variations in favor of female students in certain contexts. Ahuja and Garutsa (2024) note that female learners often receive poorer science education, which may influence their performance and participation. However, recent evidence suggests that peer tutoring may benefit both genders equally. Khalil and Wright (2022) found no significant gender-related differences in the effectiveness of peer tutoring.

Given the persistent decline in Physics performance in Gombe State and the limited implementation of peer tutoring as a teaching strategy, there is a critical need to explore its potential in enhancing students' academic performance. Therefore, this study investigated Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy as an Effective Tool for Enhancing Senior Secondary Students' Academic Performance in Physics in Gombe State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The persistent poor performance of secondary school students in Physics in Gombe State has become a critical educational concern. Data obtained from the Examination Unit of the Gombe State Ministry of Education reveal a consistently low pass rate over the past six years: 28% in 2018, 27% in 2019, 20% in 2020, 29% in 2021, 16% in 2022, and a further decline to 15% in 2023. This pattern reflects a disturbing downward trend in students' mastery of Physics, a subject essential for science, technology, and national development.

The continuing decline in students' performance has been linked to several factors, including the persistent use of ineffective, teacher-centered instructional methods that do not promote students' understanding or engagement (Nzeadibe, 2016). Consequently, many students complete secondary school without the required O'level credit in Physics needed to access science and technology-related programmes in tertiary institutions. The problem is even more pronounced among female students, who often record lower participation and performance in Physics-related subjects.

This sustained underachievement has serious implications for Gombe State. It limits the state's ability to compete favourably with other regions in terms of admission into science-based programmes, employment opportunities in STEM fields, and technological advancement. Over time, this may leave the state at a disadvantage within the national development landscape. Since Physics plays a foundational role in technological and scientific progress, the broader national implications include a reduced pool of qualified candidates for science-related careers and slower national development.

Given these challenges, there is an urgent need to identify and implement more effective teaching strategies that can enhance students' understanding and performance in Physics. Peer tutoring has been recognized as a promising learner-centered instructional strategy capable of improving academic achievement through increased interaction, collaboration, and support among students. However, its use in Physics classrooms in Gombe State appears limited. Therefore, this study seeks to determine the effectiveness of the Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy in improving the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Physics in Gombe State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to determine the Peer Tutoring Instructional Strategy an effective tool for enhancing Senior Secondary Students' Academic Performance in Physics in Gombe State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to determine:

1. the effect of peer tutoring teaching strategy on students' academic performance in physics
2. the effect of peer tutoring teaching strategy on male and female students' academic performance in physics
3. the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on students' academic performance.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were answered:

1. What is the mean difference in the pretest and post-test academic performance scores of students taught with peer tutoring and those taught with conventional teaching method?
2. What is the mean difference in the pretest and post-test academic performance scores of male and female students in physics taught with peer tutoring?

HYPOTHESES

Based on the purpose, the following null hypotheses are formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught with peer tutoring teaching strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean of academic performance scores of male and female students taught with peer tutoring teaching strategy.

HO₃: There is no significant interaction effect of teaching methods and gender on academic performance of physics students.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group design, employing intact classes to avoid disrupting school activities. The population consisted of 4,727 SS II Physics students in public schools across Gombe State, from which a sample of 204 students was selected from four co-educational schools in Gombe LGA. The treatment group consisted of 99 students, while 105 students formed the control group. Data were collected using the Physics Students Performance Test (PSPT), a 50-item multiple-choice test based on WAEC-identified difficult Physics topics. The instrument was validated by subject experts and a measurement specialist, and a trial test using 30 students yielded a KR-21 reliability coefficient of 0.78. Data collection occurred in three phases: pre-test, six-week treatment, and post-test. The control group was taught using conventional methods, while the experimental group received peer tutoring, with high-achieving students serving as peer tutors under teacher supervision. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to answer the research questions, while ANCOVA was employed to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level. Null hypotheses were rejected when $p < .05$.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What is the mean difference in the pretest and post-test academic performance scores of students taught with peer tutoring and those taught with conventional teaching method?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pretest and Posttest Scores of Students in the Experimental Group and Control Group

Group	n	Pretest		Posttest		Mean difference
		Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
Experimental Group	99	25.35	9.41	72.81	17.12	19.91
Control Group	105	29.27	12.36	52.90	13.61	

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test scores for students in the experimental (peer tutoring) and control (conventional teaching) groups. The experimental group had a pre-test mean score of 25.35 (SD = 9.41) and a post-test mean score of 72.81 (SD = 17.12). In contrast, the control group had a higher pre-test mean score of 29.27 (SD = 12.36) but a lower post-test mean score of 52.90 (SD = 13.61). The mean difference between the two groups' post-test scores is 19.91, indicating that students taught using peer tutoring performed significantly better than those taught using conventional methods. To determine whether this difference is statistically significant, the data was subjected to further analysis of ANCOVA in Table 5.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in the pretest and post-test academic performance scores of male and female students in physics taught with peer tutoring?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pretest and post test Mean Scores of Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

Gender	n	Pretest		Posttest		Mean difference
		Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	
Male	39	29.13	9.04	76.21	17.31	5.61
Female	60	22.90	8.88	70.60	16.78	

Table 2 compares the pre-test and post-test scores of male and female students in the experimental group who were taught using peer tutoring. Male students had a pre-test mean score of 29.13 (SD = 9.04) and a post-test mean score of 76.21 (SD = 17.31). Female students had a lower pre-test mean score of 22.90 (SD = 8.88) but achieved a post-test mean score of 70.60 (SD = 16.78). The mean difference between the post-test scores of male and female students is 5.61, indicating that male students outperformed female students in terms of academic achievement after the peer tutoring intervention. Although both genders showed significant improvement in their academic performance, the higher mean score for males suggests they benefited slightly more from the peer tutoring strategy in terms of academic performance. To test whether this difference is significant, the data is subject to ANCOVA analysis.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught with peer tutoring teaching strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA of Difference in the Mean Academic Performance of Students in the Experimental Group

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	20262.729 ^a	2	10131.365	42.464	.000	.297	
Intercept	107305.128	1	107305.128	449.757	.000	.691	
Pretest	57.636	1	57.636	.242	.624	.001	
Teaching methods	19957.486	1	19957.486	83.649	.000	.294	
Error	47955.565	201	238.585				
Total	866594.000	204					
Corrected Total	68218.294	203					

a. R Squared = .297 (Adjusted R Squared = .290)

The ANCOVA results presented in Table 3 indicate a significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught with peer tutoring and those exposed to conventional teaching method. The F-value for teaching methods is 83.649, (df 1,203) and the associated p-value is less than 0.05 (Sig. = 0.000), suggesting that the null hypothesis (H_{01}) be rejected. This means that teaching method significantly affects students' academic performance, with peer tutoring showing a significant difference in performance compared to conventional teaching methods. The partial eta squared value of 0.294 indicates a moderate effect size, implying that about 29.4% of the variance in academic performance can be explained by the teaching method used.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean of academic performance scores of male and female students taught with peer tutoring teaching strategy.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA of Difference in the Mean of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	797.854 ^a	2	398.927	1.371	.259	.028	
Intercept	51814.988	1	51814.988	178.049	.000	.650	
Pre – test	55.259	1	55.259	.190	.664	.002	
Gender	545.327	1	545.327	1.874	.174	.019	
Error	27937.500	96	291.016				
Total	553536.000	99					
Corrected Total	28735.354	98					

a. R Squared = .028 (Adjusted R Squared = .008)

In Table 4, the ANCOVA results show that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught using peer tutoring. The F-value for gender is 1.874 (df 1), with a p-value of 0.174, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. This suggests that gender does not significantly impact the academic

performance of students in the peer tutoring condition, and thus, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is not rejected. The partial eta squared value of 0.019 indicates a very small effect size, reinforcing the conclusion that gender does not play a significant role in performance.

HO₃: There is no significant interaction effect of teaching methods and gender on academic performance of physics students.

Table 5: Summary of ANCOVA of Interaction Effect of Teaching Methods and Gender on Academic Achievement of Physics Students

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	20954.496 ^a	4	5238.624	22.057	.000	.307
Intercept	97558.874	1	97558.874	410.763	.000	.674
Pretest	6.585	1	6.585	.028	.868	.000
Teaching method	20144.688	1	20144.688	84.817	.000	.299
Gender	309.601	1	309.601	1.304	.255	.007
Teaching methods * Gender	401.491	1	401.491	1.690	.195	.008
Error	47263.798	199	237.507			
Total	866594.000	204				
Corrected Total	68218.294	203				

a. R Squared = .307 (Adjusted R Squared = .293)

Table 5 presents the results of an ANCOVA examining the interaction effect of teaching methods and gender on academic achievement. The interaction term of teaching methods * gender has an F-value of 1.690, with a p-value of 0.195, which is greater than 0.05. This suggests that there is no significant interaction effect between teaching methods and gender on students' academic achievement. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{05}) is not rejected, indicating that the combined influence of teaching methods and gender does not significantly affect academic performance. The partial eta squared value of 0.008 reflects a very small effect size, further suggesting that the interaction effect is negligible.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The finding of the study revealed that there is significant difference in the academic performance of students taught with peer tutoring teaching strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in favour of those taught with peer tutoring. This finding suggests that peer tutoring enhances learning by promoting student collaboration, active participation, and reinforcement of knowledge through peer interactions. The finding aligns with findings of several previous studies. For instance, John and Peter (2020), Olu and Adedayo (2018), Nwachukwu and Okafor (2019), and Wasiu & Taiwo (2017) all found that peer tutoring significantly improved students' academic performance, particularly in mathematics, science, and technical subjects. Similarly, Agu and Samuel (2018), Ogundola (2017), and John (2016) reported that peer tutoring was more effective than conventional teaching methods in enhancing students' cognitive achievement. However, Zechariah (2016) found that the Jigsaw learning strategy was more effective than peer tutoring in improving students' academic achievement in algebra. Despite this exception, the overall agreement among previous studies supports the view that peer tutoring is a beneficial instructional strategy for improving students' academic performance.

The finding of the study also revealed that there is no significant difference in the of academic performance of male and female students taught with peer tutoring teaching strategy. The finding that gender does not significantly affect academic performance when using peer tutoring implies that the method provides an equitable learning environment for both male and female students. This suggests that peer tutoring fosters an inclusive setting where students, regardless of gender, have equal opportunities to benefit from collaborative learning. The effectiveness of peer tutoring for both genders may be attributed to its ability to cater to diverse learning styles, ensuring that all students engage actively in the learning process. The finding aligns with the findings of Zechariah (2016), who also found no significant influence of gender on students' achievement. Similarly, Awofala and Agbolade (2023) reported that peer tutoring significantly improved students' achievement in mathematics, with no significant effect of gender. However, this finding contradicts the studies by Olu and Adedayo (2018), Nwachukwu & Okafor (2019), and Wasiu and Taiwo (2017), all of which reported that female students exhibited higher motivation and, in some cases, better academic performance in peer-tutored groups. Additionally, Agu and Samuel (2018) found a significant difference in achievement between male and female students, with female students performing better. These conflicting results suggest that while peer tutoring may generally benefit all students, gender-based variations in academic performance may be influenced by contextual factors such as subject area, instructional implementation, and classroom dynamics.

Additionally, the finding of the study revealed that there is no significant interaction effect of teaching method and gender on academic achievement of physics students. This means that while peer tutoring enhances performance, its effect is not dependent on whether the student is male or female. Both genders respond similarly to the instructional method, further supporting the conclusion that peer tutoring is a universally effective strategy for improving student learning outcomes in physics. The finding which reveals no significant interaction effect of teaching method and gender on academic achievement of physics students, is somewhat aligned with the findings of Zechariah (2016), who reported that gender had no significant impact on students' achievement when using different instructional strategies, including peer tutoring. However, it diverges from studies like Ogundola (2017) and Agu and Samuel (2018), which found gender to influence academic performance under certain instructional strategies, with female students often performing better. In the context of physics, the absence of a significant interaction effect in the current study might suggest that the peer tutoring strategy, when applied in a physics classroom, does not favor one gender over the other in terms of academic achievement. This could also imply that the instructional approach itself, rather than gender, plays a more crucial role in students' success in physics. The lack of a significant interaction effect in the current study could be due to differences in subject-specific challenges and students characteristics. Physics, as a subject, might present unique cognitive demands, and it is possible that peer tutoring was less effective in improving academic achievement for students in this field, especially when compared to subjects like mathematics or technical drawing. Another possible reason for this discrepancy could be the difference in how peer tutoring was implemented. Previous studies may have employed more structured or frequent peer tutoring sessions, leading to more noticeable improvements in academic performance, particularly among female students.

CONCLUSION

The study found that peer tutoring significantly improved students' academic performance in physics compared to the conventional teaching method. The strategy benefited both male and female students equally, as no significant gender difference or interaction effect was observed. These results indicate that peer tutoring is an effective and gender-inclusive approach for enhancing physics achievement among senior secondary school students in Gombe State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should adopt and integrate structured peer tutoring strategies into physics instruction to improve students' understanding and overall achievement.
2. Teachers should implement peer tutoring confidently across mixed-gender classrooms, ensuring equal participation and support for both male and female students.
3. Policymakers and curriculum planners should promote peer tutoring as a universally effective instructional approach that can be applied broadly without the need for gender-specific modifications.

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